

Metacognition and Study Skills of Arts and Science College Students

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INTRODUCTION

The study skills refers to a huge array of personality traits, attitudes, thinking processes and behaviours-all of which are related to how a person approaches a learning task. Study skills or study strategies are approaches applied to learning. They are discrete techniques that can be learned, usually in a short time and applied to all or most fields of study. They should therefore be distinguished from strategies that are specific to a particular field of study, *for example*: music or technology and from abilities inherent in the student, such as aspects of intelligence or learning styles. In this way, the metacognition is one of the grails of education. It defines as knowledge and beliefs about thinking and the factors affecting thinking which regulate 'the articulation of strategy and knowledge' (Pressley, 1998) and also Brown (1987) explores this field more deeply defining two broad and inter-related dimensions: Knowledge of cognition (knowledge about when and how to use them) and regulation of cognition (planning, supervision and assessment of the regulations processes of one's own learning).

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Effective academic learning requires high and sustained intellectual efficiency which requires high cognition. Education is to develop metacognition and study skills of arts and college students. Metacognition refers to an individual's (students) knowledge, control and awareness of his/her learning processes. Here, the study skills are more competent and very important in helping students to learning an achieving good gadget. These skills are easy to learning in short time and applicable to all kinds of subjects which give the knowledge and ideas to begin with profession career and transformation of inborn or innate qualities and concealed or hidden strength of the individual into application (utility). Thus, the arts and science students have to identify the requisite skills, knowledge, competences and strategies to learn education and to equip all experiences with such skills, regulation, knowledge and competency so that a complete transformation will be possible for an individual's good and ill. Therefore, the investigator wants to find the relationship between metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students. The present study differs from the studies reviewed earlier in terms of population, area and sample; hence the present investigation gains its relevance and significance.

OBJECTIVES

1. To find out whether there is any significant difference between men and women in their metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between arts and science college students in their metcognition and study skills.
3. To find out the relationship between Metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students.

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NULL HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their Metacognition and its dimensions.
2. There is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their study skills and its dimensions.
3. There is no significant difference between arts and science college students in their metacognition and its dimensions.
4. There is no significant difference between arts and science college students in their Study Skills and its dimensions.
5. There is no significant relationship between Metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students.

METHODOLOGY

The survey method was followed for the present study, since it is a fact finding expedition. The subjects for this investigation were taken from the students studying in the arts and science colleges in tiruchirappalli district, tamil nadu, India.

The sample size was 237 arts and science college students were taken for this investigation. It was selected by using stratified random sampling technique. Special attention was given to such factors as gender, subject, locality and educational qualification. This study tried to find out the relationship between metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students.

The tools used for the present study, Metacognition Inventory by Punitha Govil (2000) and Study Skills check list by Dr. P. Annaraja and Fr. D. Thomas Alexander (2001). The statistical techniques were used for the present study: percentage analysis, 't' test and Pearson' product moment correlation analysis.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Findings based on the hypotheses and followed by data analysis are given as follows:

Table – 1: Difference Between Men and Women Arts and Science College Students in Their Metacognition And Its Dimensions

METACOGNITION	MEN (N=129)		WOMEN (N=108)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Knowledge of Cognition	39.12	8.06	39.29	8.38	0.161	NS
Regulation of Cognition	41.37	8.27	40.14	8.66	1.117	NS
Metacognition	80.25	16.08	79.44	16.25	0.385	NS

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

FINDING-1: The table-1 shows that there is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their knowledge of cognition, regulation of cognition as the calculated't' values 0.161 and 1.117 are lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their metacognition, because the calculated't' value is 0.385 which is lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the men arts and science college students are better metacognition than the women arts and science college students. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table – 2: Difference Between Men and Women Arts and Science College Students in Their Study Skills And Its Dimensions

STUDY SKILLS	MEN (N=129)		WOMEN (N=108)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Time Scheduling	5.13	0.76	5.21	0.74	0.822	NS
Concentration	4.84	0.83	4.92	0.76	0.771	NS
Listening & Note Taking	4.51	0.98	4.36	1.11	1.160	NS
Reading Skill	8.93	1.57	8.98	1.52	0.215	NS
Preparation of Exam	4.38	1.02	4.53	1.06	1.099	NS
Writing Skill	4.43	1.02	4.67	1.00	1.822	NS
Study Skills (General)	32.25	3.37	32.69	2.74	1.085	NS

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

FINDING-2: The table-2 shows that there is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their time scheduling, concentration, listening and note taking, reading skill, preparation of exam and writing skill as respective calculated 't' values 0.822, 0.771, 1.160, 0.215, 1.099 and 1.822 are lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their study skills, because the calculated 't' value is 1.085 which is lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the women arts and science college students are better study skills than the men arts and science college students. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table – 3 : Difference Between Arts and Science College Students in their Metacognition And Its Dimensions

METACOGNITION	ARTS (N=122)		SCIENCE (N=115)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Knowledge of Cognition	40.54	7.00	37.77	9.11	2.637	S
Regulation of Cognition	42.12	7.17	39.43	9.47	2.471	S
Metacognition	82.40	14.02	77.20	17.77	2.508	S

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

FINDING-3: The table-3 shows that there is significant difference between arts and science group of arts and science college students in their knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition, because the calculated 't' values 2.637 and 2.471 are greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the arts group of arts and science college students are better in their knowledge of cognition and in their regulation of cognition than the science group of arts and science college students. In general there is significant difference between arts and science group of arts and science college students in their metacognition, since the calculated 't' value is 2.508 which is greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean score, the arts group arts and science college students are better in their metacognition than the science group arts and science college students. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table – 4 : Difference Between Men and Women Arts and Science College Students in their Study Skills and Its Dimensions

STUDY SKILLS	ARTS (N=122)		SCIENCE (N=115)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Time Scheduling	5.09	0.74	5.25	0.75	1.653	NS
Concentration	4.77	0.74	4.99	0.85	2.047	S
Listening & Note Taking	4.25	0.96	4.65	1.09	2.974	S
Reading Skill	9.00	1.26	8.90	1.80	0.514	NS
Preparation of Exam	4.56	1.06	4.33	1.01	1.677	NS
Writing Skill	4.42	1.01	4.66	1.01	1.840	NS
Study Skills (General)	32.12	3.33	32.80	2.81	1.708	NS

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

FINDING – 4: The table-4 shows that there is significant difference between arts and science group arts and science college students in their concentration and listening and note taking as the calculated 't' values 2.047 and 2.974 are greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the science group arts and science college students are better in their concentration and listening and note taking than the arts group of arts and science college students. Regarding the dimensions of study skills are time scheduling, reading skill, preparation of exam and writing skill, there exists no significant difference between arts and science group arts and science college students in their study skills, because the calculated 't' values 1.653, 0.514, 1.677 and 1.840 are lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between arts and science group of arts and science college students in their study skills, since the calculated 't' value is 1.708 which is greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean scores, the science group arts and science college students are better in their study skills than the arts group of arts and science college students. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table – 5: Relationship Between Metacognition and Study Skills of Arts and Science College Students

METACOGNITION	Calculated 'γ' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Knowledge of Cognition	0.152	S
Regulation of Cognition	0.101	NS
Metacognition	0.118	S

(At 5% level of significance for 235df, the table value of γ is 0.113)

FINDING – 5: The table-4 shows there is significant relationship between the dimensions of metacognition like knowledge of cognition and study skills of arts and science college students, since the respective calculated 'γ' values 0.148 and 0.178 are greater than the table value 0.062 at 5% level of significance. With regards to there is no significant relationship between the dimensions of metacognition like regulation of cognition of arts and science college students as the calculated

' γ ' values 0.152 and 0.118 are greater than the table value 0.113 at 5% level of significance. In general there is significant relationship between metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students, because the calculated ' γ ' value 0.118 is greater than the table value 0.113 at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

CONCLUSION

It could be elaborating from the findings a significant relationship between metacognition and study skills of arts and science college students. In this the challenges of study skills like time scheduling, concentration, listening and note taking skill, reading skill, writing skill and preparation of examination, have to develop skills which will not become obsolete. The metacognitive strategies are essential for the twenty-first century, because the strategies are usually conceptualized as an inter-related set of competencies for learning and thinking and include many of the skills required for active learning, critical thinking reflective judgment, problem solving and decision-making, this will enable students to successfully cope with new situations. Moreover, it appears that arts and science college students can adaptable, adjustable and life long learner to a varied situations and can demonstrate effective study skills in his/her education.

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